

The Concept of Agile Project management and Career Paths in Schools

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Abstract

Many personal instances factored in best practices of educators, where they are looked upon as knowledge banks and principals as the lead as providers/givers of solutions to the many prevalent issues and expectations. In leading teams in career path management, many organizations nowadays are preparing for the expected becoming the new norm in line with projected imminent shift in blending traditional in-school presence and distance learning. Building self-efficacy in schools is examined in this essay to evaluate the extent to which project management evolved and progressing. Delegating ownership empowers individuals to promote the broader organization in gaining workplace fore-experiences, highly desired for content analysis skills, through distributed leadership. The "sensemaking" concept in linking strategies is to forge ahead with unique practices that culminate in potential effective leadership in charting career paths.

Introduction/Overview

In daily supplications/assignments pursuance, individuals and organizations take on small and large forms of projects. Small and large business owners manage agencies by first conceiving ideas, then taken to the next level in planning and taking visibility studies to understand how the connoisseurs run the business. These connoisseurs are those who have been in business and have made strides and, more especially, their experiences in succeeding because they learned from past shortfalls in leaping forward in productivity. This analysis applies to school/classroom management by principals and teachers under the school divisions/districts. Typical of a school division-wide agile project management (APM) in the recall is the recent on-going plans to blend the Frontier School Division's (FSD) teaching and learning with online platform accessibility. The APM, according to Larson and Gray (2018, p. 582), is said to "relate to the rolling wave of planning and scheduling project methodology." Sliger also gave the APM definition as an iterative approach and related it to software development (Larson & Gray, 2018; Sliger, 2011). On the one hand, APM's concomitance to educating is where this essay focus. In this paper, the interest is on how small or large projects in educational institutions considered aligning with planning, implementing, estimating, monitoring, and evaluating concerning APM using the "waterfall approach" (Larson & Gray, 2018).

Larson and partner states that an APM relies on incremental, iterative development cycles to complete projects. Sometimes interchanged with agile, the Scrum, is "a substitute for work breakdown structure (WBS), uses the product features as deliverables in delivering useful functions to customers/clientele" (Larson & Gray, 2018, p. 585). Despite the above-stated facts, it traditionally noted (Sliger, 2011) that APM categorizes into three folds, namely, the Scrum, Kanban, and Extreme programming (XP). Ideas in compiling this paper tilts on the Scrum as an

agile methodology designed to manage teams (Sliger, 2011) in iterative and incremental delivery, and synonymous to how educators plan and execute teaching with expectations.

The expectation is to reflect on the versatility in focus, in evaluating project management careers (PMC), and more especially assessing and evaluating students. In furtherance is to explain the stepwise process in allowing school teams to respond quickly, efficiently, and effectively in adapting to change. Examples in tilting on scrum approach include arranging and putting students on, (a) out of school "work education programs," (b) on campus work-education trades programs, and (c) teaching technology on how to migrate to the Microsoft 365 Office in enabling the use of the teams feature for remote workshops and teaching. Out of the examples leads to the questions, *what products are schools preparing? Are educational institutions making and graduating academically bankrupt students or holistic people to take up leadership mantle? How effective would the introduction of an "assignment timeline gauge" support teachers and students to keep track of learning?* It is delightful to mention/discuss these as ways of mentoring in career paths, for teaching and practical hands-on apprenticeship (aviation, tradesmanship, and laboratory technician). The timebox is an example for use as a guide in teaching how to log and manage time equitably in school, home, and at workplaces with focus.

Highlights to Agile Project Management

APM is an iterative and incremental (Larson & Gray, 2018; Sliger, 2011). Borrowing APM methodology in managing *kindergarten to grade twelve (K-12)* educational institutions demands collaboration of self-organized and cross-functional teams. Therefore, the argument by Hornstein for the need to integrate project management culture for organizational change in current trends in school management (Hornstein, 2015). The application of the concept is to shift for use as a tool in school administrations. The momentum generated through Scrum foster insight; whose results focus approach skill acquisition in the development of managers/school leaders with the aim of student growth. The prospects of project management careers within the banking sectors, construction, manufacturing, and other service industries all stand high chance to benefit because of the iterative collaboration flare attached to the use of technology to accelerate work (Hering, 2019). All these areas, including education, seek to promote efficiency by improving human resource management (HRM) practices (Masum et al., 2015). What influences the managerial processes to include the logistics and time buffers to counteract uncertainties that are eminent in the course of project implementations.

The Present and Future of Project Management (PM)

In terms of internal coherence, an agile methodological application delivers what the clientele wants and considers means to time meeting needs. With such notion running as mindsets, there is the demand to find the high chances of curtailing time waste spent in modeling and putting into practice interventional models to guide learners on threading in wrong directions. The probability of encountering a faster organizes machinery in school governance and an increase in students' disposition aside parent's satisfaction or dissatisfaction will bring up iterations to things hoped for, evidence of things not seen, and hopefully very swiftly.

Considering the evolving nature of configuration management, as a system, we cannot wait for research to put us on the path of growth until leaders move their organizations on a robust proficient problem-based analytic complex projects.

These projects may suffer glitches along the way in their implementations and demands persistence, as witnessed in interventional measures in educational institutions (Whyte et al., 2015). Living and practicing APM in school projects, whether for the classroom, outdoor education, and keeping a school building/community safe, is by seeking the value of all people and endeavoring in eliminating time waste in rework (Whyte et al., 2015). Many personal instances factor in here, where educators are looked upon as knowledge banks and the principal as the sole lead as providers or givers of solutions to the many prevalent issues and expectations. In leading teams in career path management (Hernández, 2016), *where then is the collaborative spirit in aspirations?*

The expectations in the future is by involving clientele (students, parents, and community/stakeholders) and those we lead at all project phases, including the requirement and delivery. Arguably, it is also best to foster inclusion in the design and construction phases, to ensure class-based and large-school/division-wide-base projects for gaining motivation for people to remain on-task and in-tune every step on the way. Extract from Larson and Gray entreats that companies/institutions with well-planned report dissemination are successfully able to meet targets, goals, and objectives. Thinking about the current trends of states of affairs globally in the phase of the pandemic calls for more extensive cooperation and following suit in the challenges in how we think and act and without procrastinating.

Using Agile Project Management in Making Schools Complete

The trends in satisfying taste/perspectives and the awareness that the "one-size-fits-all" strategy is outmoded is the replacement with blended ways of engaging. Fitting the trends in the implementation of hybrid methods that best suit scenarios is where projects get pursued in iterative and incremental steps in the school's best practices. Some charge carries exceptionally more extensive work-based and tackling tasks with multiple project managers spread over sizeable geographical map makes it difficult to accomplish. For example, *what is an authentic assessment, where does it take place, and how does it look? Who benefits from an authentic assessment?* Teachers may have too many test data at the school level, but how much data is enough for us to evaluate a student is something to decipher. To address these facets, it is also necessary to consider infrastructure, retaining combine management of teacher hiring and workflow, as well as logistics and student management. Thinks also about making teachers relaxed to do the things they do best based on their training (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012).

Infrastructure. Comprises of the underlying physical and organizational structures and facilities, including buildings, power supplies, desks, to mention a few when it concerns a school. Other types include communication gadgets such as fax machines and telephones, transportation to transport students, sewage, clean drinking water, health, and budget systems. These things are needed for the smooth and effective operations of a school community and also having in place, dispatch building team to regularly inspect and maintain school building/properties befitting standards.

Talking about students travel on school buses from and to school, there is mounting pressure on parents on how to get children to school with school reopening in September 2020.

A collaborative consensus of sharing duties is the only way to move forward, considering the fragile states of many broken homes and where children live in two homes. In a typical school in a division to note (personal observations) indicate, there are more half of the student population from two households, two-thirds have single parents, and over sixty percent live on their own and without vehicles to drive. All these synopses make the situation come September 2020 when school reopens very uncertain.

Retain Management in Teacher Workflow. Extract from the "waterfall approach" by Larson and Gray (2018, p. 581) alluding to the planning stage (concept phase- CP); it is the duty of all teachers to about what to include in lessons. Teachers go through a series of workshops from different locations and online professional developments on how to instruct. In recent times, engagement has been about learning the new platform of "Microsoft 365 Office teams" to assist in online distance delivery. Since the platform is unique, it is incumbent to train teaching, and non-teaching staff regards how it is operated in readiness to work with it in the near foreseeable future. The orientation is in line with the projected imminent shift in blending traditional in-school presence and distance learning. This preparation thwarts uncertainties that will result in educating in the post-COVID-19 pandemic. In the "waterfall approach" requirement phase (RP), for instance, educators think about teaching aids required for learning by students. In this phase, access to smartboard and technology with a blend of old-school traditional methods of paper and pencil is carefully organized and in sequence to make teaching-learning combination a complete process. *How do educators feel when we hear from students, "I do not want to be a teacher?"* Maybe it could be because the blend in the RP stage was not well received or a poor teacher-learner relationship.

Linking the RP to the design and construction phases, reference is to educator's thinking of assessment as, for, and of learning. In the diagnostics, formative, and summative evaluation, respectively, think in part of the whole teaching and learning as a progression. Questions to define gaps in testing observed include but not limited to; *(a) how much to teach per lesson (b) what teaching style will be adapted, and (c) how frequently is assessment performed and used and with what assessment criteria protocols?* Contained in these statements is like asking the crucial question of school/instructional leaders making sense as posited by Tsekeni and associates (2020), in testing and using test scores to design evaluation in subject disciplines. In this light, an invitation to the use of "GRASP," an acronym expanded to mean, 'given, required, analysis, solution, and paraphrasing' is possible in problem-solving. In the training process for teachers in drone flying is another area worth mentioning, sponsored by the Canadian Aviation Regulation Advisory Council (CCRAC) in conjunction with the Frontier School Division Pilot Network (FSDPN). Bringing in hands-on activities into lessons promote interest amongst student. Teachers undergo training and use the knowledge gained to teach and lead students. When students become masters in what they do, they also acquire skills that orient them in career paths through self-efficacy building.

The testing and deploy phases contain how to manage productivity/test scores to reflect employees' or learners' level of knowledge and what would be the nature of adjudication in the form of awarding incentives for workers or numeric value grade to learners. The challenge is a difficult one, and revelations from one organizational standpoint may differ from others but applicable in other fields. Practical administrative skills in the ability to plan, organize, direct, and control individuals/groups of people to achieve specific itemized goals as defined by APM protocols and to ensure success by all standards, with schools in the heart of consideration ("*A*

guide to the project management body of knowledge," 2017). The very reason why carefulness and wait time becomes a substantial factor in mentoring beginners in a culture of nurturing learning.

Logistics and Students Management. In line with this protocol, all teachers well familiar with the Microsoft 365 Office software, would be ready to handle lessons with confidence to work with students either in school or learn from home. A point to note is that, when it was challenging to have all learners assimilate concepts easily during the face-to-face encounter in the classroom, then the expectation will be high when learning from home using technology/Internet/apps. The progression in the analysis of how people/students cope in managing time spent on assignments, performance task, laboratory work, and technology use add to the insights that school-managers must know to be able to support learners.

Work-education and Orienting in Technology of recent times to get software and operation platforms updates in Microsoft 365 office usage is taking over as a tool to engage teaching and learning. Offering students, the opportunity to lead a class in problem-solving on the whiteboard, smartboard, in Microsoft teams, and overhead projectors use, including paper and pencil, are all part of technology. The protocols that need to be learned by teachers in addition to functioning in their daily classroom structure and routines have changed, and more challenges are looming in the coronavirus era as we face. The managerial act of brisk sequential pacing viewed either as small/large scale whole-school practice fosters study and personal skills in learners. It offers teachers ways to spot struggling students to put in early interventions. The interventions, which also founded in the continuum of teaching, learning, assessments, evaluating, and post-secondary education, are based on decision-making as a collective understanding amongst families and school staff (Ahmad et al., 2017).

Decision-making in assessing and evaluating students in schools, the purpose is to introduce and maintain a profile in maximizing the robustness of scheduled buffers. The buffer in context is creating flexibility criteria, where for example, students have freedom, to write tests/examinations in separate rooms if they so request, and at the same time managing risk (Ghoddousi et al., 2017). Evaluating school project management within FSD in schools and as a whole unit, for example, has seen growth in allowing student's freedom in selecting their work placement sites during "work-education." The freedom is comparable to the analysis of career path progressions (Marion et al., 2014). The freedom of choice has given students flexibility in gaining hands-on experience in the occupation of their interest and further prepares them for future careers. In evaluating teachers and principals in the capacity of PM role is a plus in terms of structure and administration but can do better. All comes to whether the new era of working and studying from home will have validity and reliability support.

Conclusion/Recommendations

Traditional project management methods fix requirements to control time and cost, but the agile control and moderate. Scrum, learned from Larson and Gray (2018), sets the time and cost to manage requirements, done using time boxes, collaborative ceremonies, a prioritized product backlog, and frequent feedback cycles in table 1 (see time box, appendix – A). Using "timeboxing," work/project/daily tasks get breakdown into set periods. This principle has allowed for more significant expansions in accomplishment more than with less organized schedule applicable practices to teachers, students, and non-teaching staff. The "sensemaking" concept (Tsekeni et al., 2020) linking to "timeboxes," schools forges ahead with unique practices that culminated in potential practical instructions. Timeboxing is reminiscent of teaching project portfolio management to motivate productivity (Young & Conboy, 2013).

In another form of supporting school management, the use of "assignment timeline gauge" is helpful. Learners become self-monitor regulators on workloads/assignments by checked marking on the monthly timeline gauge dashboard (see appendix B). Problem-solving skills teaching override the abysmal preparation and graduating academically bankrupt students. For example, using the "GRASP" concept to solve physics and mathematics word problems, students can break big questions in incremental repeated stages with flow. Students take note of parameters and follow through with formula in an analysis where given parameters are substituted to perform a solution. In conclusion, students paraphrase the answer by casting complete statements in gaining two advantages, namely, gaining proficiency in numeracy and literacy skills.

Building on skills, supplementing efforts in the workflow in specific subjects, and maintaining management, for example, in hands-on drone flying in gaining experience, has been

efficient. The efficiency from work education outreach and in-school coaching in job-related career subjects such as technology are welcome. Maintaining management is in two folds. First, it ensures awareness of the legal battles that can surface in careers, such as violating restricted spaces in drone piloting. Learners are delegated ownership and empowered in gaining personal workplace fore-experience, with highly desired content analysis skills (Karanja & Grant, 2020). Distributed leadership is at its best in avoiding adverse outcomes through confidence building indicator skills in successful teamwork PM (Flavin, 2018). Secondly, students also become aware of what to gather in each through learning to meet the requirements of new career paths (Transport Canada, 2019). Given the account of the financial cost, legal battles that can ensue, and ways of using knowledge gain without breaching protocols, many project managers are enlightened in school departments in becoming more focused.

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Appendix – A: An In-depth Guide to Timeboxing

	Individual		Group work		Administration
	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
Time slots					
School and Home Routines					
Science, Math, Social, Prep. & Assessment/Quizzes/Tests					
09:00-10:30 [4:30-5:00]					
10:30-12:00 [5:00-5:30]					
1:00-2:30 [5:30-6:30]					
2:30-3:00 Bedtime stories to Sleep [6:30-7:30]					

Table 1: Timeboxing Planner to aid Individual Learning

Appendix – B: Assignment Submission Timeline Gauge

September []

Students Names	Week 1			Week 2			Week 3			Week 4		
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8	D9	D10	D11	D12
S1												
S2												
S3												
S4												

Table 1: Timeline Gauge for Teaching and Learning

Legend:
 S1, S2, S3 ... are students
 D1, D2, D3 are the assignments to be submitted.